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ASSESSING THE ROLE OF PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT IN ENHANCING BUSINESS EDUCATORS' COMMITMENT IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA

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This study was conducted to assess the influence that perceived organization support (POS) has on commitment of business educators in federal tertiary institutions in south-south, Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Population for the study was 92. Owing to the small number, the entire population was used as the sample size. Data for the study was sourced from both primary and secondary source. Primary source was from administered copies of questionnaire. Research instrument was a structured Likert scale questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and simple linear regression statistical tools were used in analyzing the collated data. Findings revealed that fairness had a moderated correlation value of $R=0.519$ with a standardized coefficient $\beta=0.418$. Supervisor support showed a standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.536$. Conclusively, perceived organizational support has a significant positive influence on the commitment of business educators in federal tertiary institutions in south-south, Nigeria. Since POS is seen as the extent to which the organization values the employees' contribution and cares about their well-being, it is believed that the employees should reciprocate such perceived support with increased commitment, loyalty and performance.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Support, Fairness, Supervisor Support, Commitment, Business Educators.

Introduction

The importance of education to any nation cannot be overemphasized. Education creates an enlightened society. It is the ultimate element that contributes a great deal in human growth and development. Iqbal and Hashmi (2015) opine that it is the pillar upon which highly developed cultures are fabricated. For this pillar to be strengthened and sustained, it is necessary to highlight its importance and upgrade the quality of education. One of the greatest means of upgrading this educational quality is by retaining committed and experienced academic staff (business educators inclusive) in higher institution of learning as the absence of this pillar makes the foundation weak and everything built on it deteriorates (Efi and Imagha, 2019).

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The degree of support academic staff members perceive from management is one of the main variables that may affect their commitment within an organization. The degree to which an organization values the contributions of its employees and is concerned about their well-being is known as perceived organizational support, or POS. According to Budi and Mugi (2023), it is the opinion of staff members regarding the assistance they obtain from the company. It represents the workers' perception of the organization's willingness to assist them when necessary to complete tasks efficiently and get through challenging circumstances. Perceptions of organizational support describe the general beliefs formed within employees regarding the extent to which the organization shows commitment to them. This is reflected through the awards given by the organization for their contribution and the attention given by the organization to aspects of their lives (Wayne *et al.*, 1997). Furthermore, the perception of organizational support can also be explained as an employee's assessment of the extent to which the organization provides support and attention to their well-being in meeting social and emotional needs arising from their contribution to the organization (Kurtessis *et al.*, 2017).

According to Dian and Mirza (2008), the most common antecedents of POS are; fairness, supervisor support and organization rewards. It is suggested that employees take active interest in the organization in which they are regarded and supported (Eisenberger, Malone and Presson, 2016). When employees perceive that they are receiving fair treatment in comparison to their coworkers, they perceive more support. Fairness can also be described as procedural justice, or the fairness of happenings in the organization. Ideally, supervisor support has to do with employees viewing their employer's actions, morals, and beliefs to be indicative and representative of the organization's actions, morals, and beliefs.

When organizations value their employees, benefits like respect and approval, pay and promotion and access to information and other aids needed to effectively carry out task will be obtained with ease. If employees perceive that they are being fairly treated and supported by the organization, the reciprocity norm opines that they should return favourable treatment (Rupp *et al.*, 2014). In this regard, both the employer and the employee apply the reciprocity norm in their relationship (favourable treatment given by one party is reciprocated and this will lead to beneficial outcomes for both of them). Perceptions are very important as people behave according to their perceptions and not on the basis of reality (Bodla, Afza and Danish, 2004).

In today's highly competitive world that is coated with rapid technological advancement, the survival of an organization or institution is tied to its competitive advantage. Employees are one of the major assets that give organizations competitive advantage over its competitors. No organization can optimize its performance except employees are committed to the organization's goals and objectives (Muda and Fook 2020). However, deepening employees' commitment as well as enhancing their retention and productivity is one of the major challenges of most organizations across the world in recent times. This challenge is however more prevalent in emerging markets and developing economies like Nigeria, considering the hydra-headed problems of human resource gap, ineffective leadership and corruption. Consequently, researchers began to explore the issues of commitment at workplace including tertiary institutions.

Employees' commitment is the feeling of devotion to one's organization, willingness to work hard for the employer and the intent to remain with the organization. Tuna, Ghazzawi, Tuna and Catir (2016) defined it as the psychological state that characterizes the employee's relationship with the organization and has implications for the decision to retain (or not) his/her membership in the organization. Employees' commitment has three dimensions; continuance, affective, and normative. Continuance commitment is the cost that employees associate

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with leaving the organization. It can also be referred to as the economic benefit of staying with the organization. Affective component refers to employees' emotional dedication to identify and be involved with the organization. While normative component represents an employee's feeling of obligation and loyalty to the organization. The concept of employees' commitment attracted considerable interest from practitioners, policy makers and academics all in an attempt to understand the intensity of an employees' dedication to the organization. As such, it is seen as an important concept in enhancing organizational effectiveness. Management scholars have linked it with useful organizational outcomes such as: increased job satisfaction, retention, and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour. These outcomes are important pre-requisites to ensure provision of adequate and qualitative educational system. As such, the importance of business educators' commitment in tertiary institutions in developing countries cannot be overemphasized.

Statement of the Problem

Perceived Organizational Support is assumed to be very essential in ensuring employees happiness in the organization. As a result, it has widely gained the interest of scholars and managers particularly in the Western and Asian economy. However, most of the studies carried out in this area only concentrated on the effect of POS on employees' job performance, level of effectiveness and job involvement; very few considered job satisfaction and employees' commitment. Of the few studies that concentrated on employees' commitment, it considered the benefit of immigrant faculties on the western economy, with no regards to the effect of negative net emigrants' faculties on developing countries.

Equally, the few empirical studies that considered the effect of POS on employees' commitment, to the researchers' knowledge, none has been carried out to assess its effect on business educators in federal universities in South-South, Nigeria. Of course, it is not uncommon to observe that in most Nigerian tertiary institutions; certain policies, work procedures, management actions and inactions by Government and management may compel faculties (business educators inclusive) to organize and interpret their sensory impressions negatively about their workplace. These actions and inactions by the Government and management are expressed through: neglected facilities, poor funding, poor remuneration, and under-equipped facilities.

Others include; unsatisfactory working conditions characterized by heavy workloads, and obsolete facilities. This has led to incessant industrial actions and threats of strikes by faculties. Unfortunately, this may lead to dysfunctional work behaviour like dampened work morale, incessant tardiness and even brain drain. These issues necessitated this study which is designed to assess if fairness, and supervisor support can help enhance business educators' commitment in federal tertiary institutions, south-south, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of this study is to assess the influence of perceived organizational support on the commitment of business educators in federal tertiary institutions in south-south, Nigeria. The specific objectives include to:

- i. examine the influence of fairness on business educators' commitment in federal tertiary institutions in south-south, Nigeria;
- ii. assess how supervisor support affects business educators' commitment in federal tertiary institutions in south-south, Nigeria;

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Research Questions

In line with the objectives of the study, the following questions were developed:

- i. How does fairness influence commitment of business educators' commitment in federal tertiary institutions in south-south, Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent does supervisor support affect commitment of business educators' commitment in federal tertiary institutions in south-south, Nigeria?

Hypotheses of the Study

Research hypotheses for this study were formulated in a null form as follow:

Ho₁: Fairness does not have a significant influence on the commitment of business educators' commitment in federal tertiary institutions in south-south, Nigeria

Ho₂: Supervisor support does not have a significant influence on the commitment of on business educators' commitment in federal tertiary institutions in south-south, Nigeria

Literature Review

Concept of Perceived Organization Support

The concept of Perceived Organizational Support gained prominence in the late 1980s (Chen, 2002 in Efi and Imagha, 2016). Organizational support theory supposes that in order to meet socio-emotional needs and to determine the organization's willingness to reward increased work performance, employees develop beliefs about the extent in which the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being (Erdogan and Enders, 2007). Eisenberger *et al*, (2016) referred to this belief as "perceived Organization support". Perceived organization support is developed by meeting employees' socio-emotional needs and indicating readiness to reward employees' extra efforts and to render help needed by employees to carry out their jobs effectively.

According to Blau (1964) in Wikhamn and Hall (2012) Perceived Organizational Support emanated from the social exchange theory which serves to explain employee-organizational relationships. This theory holds sway that each party has perceptions and expectations regarding the behavior of the other party, but these perceptions and expectations are related with the timing or the specifics of what each party must give/offer. When both parties benefit from the exchange, neither of them will know whether the expectations of the other have been fully met. Hence, the social exchange involves reciprocity (Tansky and Cohen, 2011). From the above postulation, Perceived Organizational Support covers the employees' "Perception" about their organization's concern with their well-being and their contributions.

Perceived Organizational Support refers to an employees' belief that the organization for which he or she works values his/her contributions and cares for his/her wellbeing (Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison and Sowa, 1986). Rahman and Karan (2012) opine that Employees with high POS believe that their organization will appreciate their added efforts that conduce to their organizations. It is believed that employees perceive their organization as being supportive when they find that the rewards are fair, when they have an opportunity for taking part in decisions and when employees see their supervisors as supportive (Rhoades, Eisenberger and Ameli, 2001). According to Eisenberger *et al*. (1986), individuals shows a consistent pattern of agreement with statements concerning whether their organizations appreciated their contributions and would treat them favourably in varying circumstances. Research shows that employees with strong POS are more likely to have higher levels of citizenship behaviours, lower level of tardiness, and better customers service (Eder and Eisenberger, 2008; Vandenberghe *et al*, 2007). For medical doctors, POS could be felt if their employers provide

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sufficient personal protective equipment, payment of hazard allowance, provision of standard laboratories and up to date hospital facilities.

Components of Perceived Organizational Support

The common antecedents of perceived organizational support are fairness, and supervisor support. Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) opine when employees perceive that they are receiving fair treatment in comparison to their coworkers, they perceive more support. The equity theory opines that employees feel entitled to what they are given as workers based on their inputs to the job. As such, fairness can be perceived even if the rewards differ in size, based on employee rank. Also, fairness can be described as procedural justice, or the fairness of happenings in the organization. The politics of the organization, or the promoting of self-interest, are often related to employees' perceptions of procedural justice. Eisenberger and Rhoades (2002) found supervisor support to be strongly related to employees' perception of support. Typically, people view their employer's actions, morals, and beliefs to be indicative and representative of the organization's actions, morals, and beliefs. POS tends to be higher when the supervisor or higher employer is thought to care about the employee's experience at work and does what he or she can to show appreciation for the work done.

Concepts of Employee Commitment

Employee Commitment has attracted considerable interest from practitioners, policy makers and academics all in an attempt to understand the intensity of an employees' dedication to the organization (Lumley, Coetzee, Tladinyane and Ferreira, 2011). Hence, it is regarded as an important concept from the viewpoint of enhancing organizational effectiveness. Oludeyi (2015) in Imagha *et al.* (2023) views commitment as a process that increasingly integrates employees' goals with those of their employers is what defines job commitment as demonstrating an employee's attitude or orientation toward an organization, which in turn is what connects or draws employees to the organization. According to Robbins and Judge (2009), employee commitment is a state in which an employee identifies with a particular organization and its goals and wishes to maintain membership in the organization. It is concerned with the degree to which an employee feels psychologically attached to the organization in which he/she works (Fu and Deshpande, 2013).

Muda and Fook (2020) opine that commitment is divided into three (3) dimensions namely; Affective, Continuance and Normative. Affective commitment (AC) is an emotional attachment to the organization and a belief in its values (Robbins and Judge, 2009). Employees that are committed affectively feel strong emotional attachment with the organization's norms and values. Individuals with high affective commitment feel themselves as part of their organizations. They attend to their organizations like a family, and feel a strong sense of belonging to their organizations. Also, Dinc (2017) opine that Continuance Commitment (CC) is the extent to which employees feel committed to their organizations by virtue of the costs that they feel are associated with leaving. It is seen as a calculative attachment that is different from Affective Commitment. This could be as a result of lack of other viable alternative job opportunities, the threat of losing attractive extrinsic or intrinsic benefits, the risk of losing a good work environment, of parting with seniority-based privileges and of undermining the job status or reputation. Normative Commitment (NC) refers to commitment based on a sense of obligation to the organization (Allen and Meyer, 1996). This type of commitment is an obligation to remain with the organization for moral or ethical reasons (Robbins and Judge, 2009). Social and moral pressures that a person encounters through cultural and family interactions while entering the organization are regarded as antecedents of Normative commitment (Meyer and Allen, 1991).

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Equity Theory

This theory was developed by a behavioral psychologist, John Stacey Adams (Baridam, 2002). The theory is useful for explaining employees' perception about fairness in matters. Equity theory explains the thought process in which employee uses to determine the fairness of management decision making. Tanner (2015) opines that the core of equity theory is that individuals judge the fairness of their treatment based on how others like them are treated. Employees tend to make social comparisons to others who are similarly situated in the organization. According to this theory, employees view a situation as equitable when employees who give similar inputs receive similar outcomes. In a situation where the rewards differ for the same degree of effort, employees view the situation as inequitable. Equity theory shows that inequities (perceived or real) harm employee motivation. Clearly, Stacey Adams in Baridam (2002) posits, "we seek social justice in how we are rewarded for our job performance". According to Baridam (2002) in a work situation, felt inequity exists when an individual feel that the rewards received in return for his contributions are relatively less (felt negative inequity) or more than (felt positive inequity) those received by others. This is represented diagrammatically in Fig 1.1

Fig. 2.2: Equity theory

Source: Baridam (2002) Management and Organization theory

Empirical Review

Efi and Imagha (2016) conducted to assess the relationship between perceived organizational support and turnover intention of academic staff in University of Uyo. The population of the study was made up of 1,451 academic staff in the employ of the institution. Sample size was determined using Taro Yamene's formulae for sample size determination in which a sample of 314 was arrived at. Sources of data were from both primary and secondary sources. Secondary source was from published articles and textbooks while primary source was from responses of the 314 copies of questionnaire administered on the respondents using convenience sampling technique. Findings showed that turnover intention of academic staff in University of Uyo is influenced by their felt negative support from the institution. For university of Uyo to attract and retain experienced academic staff, Management of the institution should strive to increase the level of support given to the academic staff by showing they care about their wellbeing and value their contribution to the institution. This study did not decompose the variables of POS while the current study has judiciously decomposed the variable of the independent variable.

Xin *et al.*, (2014) conducted study to (a) examine the correlation between POS and Job Performance; (b) identify the predictors of POS, including demographic and organizational characteristics among faculty members at a Chinese university; (c) investigate the influence of mediating factors between POS and JP; and (d) compare the findings of this study with related studies. A cross-sectional questionnaire survey was used in this study. The questionnaire was administered to 700 faculty members who were randomly selected from all faculty members at six universities. A total of 581 questionnaires were obtained. A statistical model for JP was developed based on the literature review. The analysis results indicated that the relationship between POS and JP was mediated by

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job satisfaction (JS), positive affectivity (PA), and affective commitment (AC). In addition, procedural and distributive justice contribute to POS. The study concludes that the relationship between POS and JP is mediated by JS, PA, and AC and is influenced by POS. These results can provide evidence for university administrators to improve POS and increase the JP of faculty members at universities. This study was conducted in an advanced economy while the current study is being conducted in a developing country.

Igbal and Hashmi (2015) conducted a study on the effect of perceived organizational support on retention of employees with mediation of psychological empowerment in higher educational institution of Pakistan. Questionnaire of 31 items was adopted in which 8 item scales was adopted to measure perceived organizational support, 12 items scale to measure psychological empowerment and 11 item scale to measure employee retention. 200 copies of questionnaire were distributed, out of which 170 were returned. Analysis of data was done using regression analysis. Finding of the study revealed the existence of considerable and affirmative association of perceived organizational support with employee retention by partial mediation of psychological empowerment.

Methodology

For this study, survey research design was adopted. This design was used since it aided the researchers to collect data directly from the respondents. Population of the study consisted of 92 Business Educators in the five Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria (Staff Nominal Roll of the five Federal Universities in the 2020/2021 academic session).

Table 1: Distribution of the Study Population

S/N.	Name of Universities	Number of Business Educators	Male	Female
1.	University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State	15	10	5
2.	University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State	29	17	12
3.	University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State	6	5	1
4.	University of Benin, Edo State	30	20	10
5.	Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State	12	9	3
Total		92	61	31

Source: Staff Nominal Roll Per University (2022).

With this small number, the entire population was used as the sample. This was informed by the assertion that, when the population is small, studying the entire population will provide higher validity and better understanding of the relationship between the variables in the study. This is in line with Osuala (2005) who opined that the entire population should be studied when the population is relatively small.

Convenience sampling technique was adopted for this study. The research instrument was a structured questionnaire which was administered to the respondents in their respective offices. Scoring of the research instrument was done using Likert Scale. In the questionnaire, the respondents responded by indicating their degree

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of agreement or disagreement to each statement by ticking along the column provided. Scoring of the questionnaire was graded as follows: Strongly agree (SA) - 5; Agree (A) – 4; Undecided (UN) – 3; Disagree (D) – 2; Strongly disagree (SD) – 1.

The descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the study. The descriptive statistics were percentage and frequency distribution tables which were used to capture respondents’ demographic characteristics and frequency distribution of the responses on the study variables. Inferential statistics was used to assess the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The simple linear regression analysis was the inferential statistics used. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22 was used to aid the analysis.

Based on the variables of this study, the simple linear regression equations are presented thus;

$$Cm = a1 + b1Fr + \dots e \quad \text{equation 1}$$

$$Cm = a2 + b2Ss + \dots e \quad \text{equation 2}$$

Where;

Cm (Y) = Commitment

Fr (X1) = Fairness

Ss (X2) = Supervisor support e= error term

a= constant

Table 2: Summary of Questionnaire Administration and Collection

Questionnaire Administered	Collected	%
Total membership copies served	92	100
Total membership copies completed corrected	79	85.9
Total membership copies incorrectly filled	4	4.4
Total membership copies not returned	9	9.7

Source: Field Survey (2024)

As indicated in Table 2, a total of 92 copies of questionnaire were distributed, 79 copies representing 85.9% were returned in useable form to the researcher, 4 copies representing 4.4% were returned but not in useable form while a total of 9 copies were not returned. Consequently, since the number returned in useable form is higher than others, the response rate being greater than half, the researchers considered this response adequate representation of the sampled frame of the study. These 79 responses therefore represent 100% of the instrument used in subsequent analysis of this study. In other words, the analyses done in this study are based on the responses obtained from these 79 respondents.

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Table 3: Research responses on Fairness

S/N	Fairness	Strong Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly	Total	
Agree (%)	(%)	(%)	(n) %	Disagree			
(%)	(%)						
1	Performance is fairly rate by considering my responsibilities	22 (27.8)	41 (51.9)	13 (16.5)	2 (2.5)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
2	The procedures used in my organization uphold ethical and moral standard	10 (12.7)	44 (55.7)	22 (27.8)	3 (3.8)	0 (0)	79 (100)
3	I am able to express my views and feelings about my organization procedures	28 (35.4)	33 (41.8)	5 (6.3)	8 (10.1)	5 (6.3)	79 (100)

Source: The Researcher’s Compilation (2024).

Table 3 shows that 22(27.8%) of the respondents strongly agree that their performance is fairly rated by considering their responsibilities; 41(51.9%) of the respondents also agree; 13(16.5%) of the respondents were neutral; while 2(2.5%) of the respondents and 1(1.3%) of the respondents strongly disagree and disagree that their performance is fairly rated by considering their responsibilities. For question 2, 10(12.7%) of the respondents strongly agree that the procedures used in their organization uphold ethical and moral standard. 44(55.7%) of the respondents also agree with the statement; 22(27.8%) of the respondents were neutral. On the other hand, 3(3.8%) of the respondents disagree that the procedures used in their organization uphold ethical and moral standard. For question 3, 28(35.4) of the respondents strongly agree that they are able to express their views and feelings about their organization procedures. 33(41.8%) agree, 5(6.3%) were undecided, 8(10.1%) disagree while 5 (6.3%) respondents strongly disagree that they are able to express their views and feelings about their organization procedures.

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Table 4: Research responses on Supervisor support

S/N	Supervisor support	Strong Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly	Total	
Agree (%)	(%)	(%)	Disagree (n) %	(n) %	(n) %	(n) %	
1	My supervisor considers viewpoints	19 (24.1)	37 (46.8)	20 (25.3)	2 (2.5)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
2	My department would forgive an honest mistake on my part. My supervisor	31 (31.2)	34 (43.0)	12 (15.2)	1 (1.3)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
3	shows concern for my rights as an employee	10 (12.7)	44 (55.7)	21 (26.6)	3 (3.8)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)

Source: The Researcher’s Compilation (2024).

Table 4 reveals that 19(24.1%) of the respondents strongly agree that their supervisor considers their viewpoints; 37(46.8%) of the respondents also agree; 20(25.3%) of the respondents were neutral; while 2(2.5%) of the respondents and 1(1.3%) of the respondents strongly disagree and disagree their supervisor considers their viewpoints. Question 2, 31(31.2%) of the respondents strongly agree that their department would forgive an honest mistake they make. 34(43.0%) of the respondents also agree with the statement; 12(15.2%) of the respondents were neutral. On the other hand, 1(1.3%) of the respondents disagree while 1(1.3%) strongly disagree that their department would forgive an honest mistake they make. For question 3, 10(12.7%) of the respondents strongly agree that their supervisor shows concern for their rights as an employee. 44(55.7%) agree, 21(26.6%) were undecided, 3(3.8%) disagree while 1 (1.3%) respondents strongly disagree that their supervisor shows concern for their rights as an employee.

Table 6: Research responses on Commitment

S/N	Commitment	Strong Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly	Total	
Agree (%)	(%)	(%)	Disagree (n) %	(n) %	(n) %	(n) %	
1	I am very passionate about my work	23 (29.1)	35 (44.3)	17 (21.5)	2 (2.5)	2 (2.5)	79 (100)
2	I really feel as if this institution’s challenges are my own. I am capable	22 (27.8)	41 (51.9)	13 (16.5)	2 (2.5)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
3	of handling my assignments without much supervision	33 (41.8)	30 (38.0)	4 (5.1)	6 (7.6)	6 (7.6)	79 (100)

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Source: The Researcher’s Compilation (2024).

Table 6 shows that 23(29.1%) of the respondents strongly agree that they very passionate about their work; 35(44.3%) of the respondents also agree; 17(21.5%) of the respondents were neutral; while 2(2.5%) of the respondents and 2(2.5%) of the respondents strongly disagree that they are very passionate about their work. For question 2, 22(27.8%) of the respondents strongly agree that they really feel as if this institution’s challenges are their own. 41(51.9%) of the respondents also agree with the statement; 13(16.5%) of the respondents were neutral. On the other hand, 2(2.5%) of the respondents disagree while 1(1.3%) strongly disagree that they really feel as if this institution’s challenges are their own. For question 3, 33(41.8%) of the respondents strongly agree that they are capable of handling their assignments without much supervision. 30(38.0%) agree, 4(5.1%) were undecided, 6(7.6%) disagree while 6(7.6%) respondents strongly disagree that they are capable of handling their assignments without much supervision.

Test of Hypotheses

Ho1: Fairness does not have a significant influence on business educators’ commitment in south-south, Nigeria.

Hi1: Fairness does have a significant influence on business educators’ commitment in south-south, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Adjusted R	Std. Error of the			
Model R	R Square	Square	Estimate	
1	.519 ^a	.270	.267	1.46636

a. Predictors: (Constant), FairTotal

ANOVA^a

Mean					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression 181.096	1	181.096	84.223	.000 ^b
	Residual 490.248	228	2.150		
Total	671.343	229			

a. Dependent Variable: CommitTotal

b. Predictors: (Constant), FairTotal

Coefficients^a

Unstandardized	Standardized				
Coefficients	Coefficients				
Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	8.889	.686	12.950	.000
	FairTotal	.418	.046	.519	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CommitTotal

Regression analysis revealed that the dependent variable was strongly correlated at R = 0.519. According to the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.270$ and the adjusted coefficient of determination; adjusted $R^2 = 0.267$, fairness explained 2.7% of variance of commitment of business educators in south-south, Nigeria. From the anova table, the statistical significance of the regression model shows that $P < 0.0005$, which is less than 0.05. This means that it is a good fit. To assess the relative importance of the dependent variable on the independent variable, beta coefficient is provided on the coefficient table. Fairness showed a significant standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.418$, P-value=0.0000. This finding can be interpreted that every 1unit change in fairness will lead to 0.41 change in

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commitment. However, since the p-value=0.000 which is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. It is concluded that fairness has a significant on commitment of business educators in south-south, Nigeria.

Ho2: Supervisor support does not have a significant influence on business educators’ commitment in south-south, Nigeria.

Hi2: Supervisor support have a significant influence on business educators’ commitment in south-south, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.617 ^a	.381	.378	1.35005

a. Predictors: (Constant), SupportTotal

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	255.782	1	255.782	140.337	.000 ^b
	Residual	415.561	228	1.823		
	Total	671.343	229			

a. Dependent Variable: CommitTotal

b. Predictors: (Constant), SupportTotal

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.		
1	(Constant)	7.308	.666	10.974	.000	
	SupportTotal	.536	.045	.617	11.846	.000

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Regression analysis showed that the dependent variable was strongly correlated at R=0.617. The coefficient of determination R²=0.381 and the adjusted coefficient of determination; adjusted R²= 0.378. Supervisor support explained 3.8% of variance of on business educators’ commitment in south-south, Nigeria. From the anova table, the statistical significance of the regression model shows that P < 0.0005, which is less than 0.05. This means that it is a good fit. In assessing the relative importance of the dependent variable on the independent variable, beta coefficient is provided on the coefficient table. Supervisor support showed a significant standardized coefficient of β=0.536, p-value=0.000. This finding shows that every 1unit change in supervisor support will lead to 0.53 change in commitment. However, since the p-value=0.000 which is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. As a result, we conclude that supervisor support has significant influence on business educators’ commitment in south-south, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

According to findings from the study, Fairness shows a strong, positive and significant relationship with doctors’ commitment. Specifically, the regression analysis indicates that fairness accounts for a sizeable part of the variance in doctors’ commitment. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Efi and Imagha (2019); Malik, Kazmi and Nadeem (2016); Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002). In their study, they found that when employees are fairly treated, it means that the organization care about their wellbeing. According to Fabiene and Kachchchap

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(2016), where organization provide fair basis for rating of employees' performance, commitment of such employees to the organization will be high. Also, it was revealed from findings in this study that supervisor support strongly and positively correlates with business educators' commitment. The regression analysis showed that supervisor support accounts for a sizeable amount of variance in business educators' commitment. This finding agrees with the finding of Abubakar (2003). In his study, he argues that when supervisors provide greater support to human resource activities, there is a significant increase in organizational commitment of employees.

Conclusion

The concept of Perceived Organizational support is seen as the extent to which the organization values the employees' contribution and cares about their well-being. It is believed that the employees should reciprocate such perceived support with increased commitment, loyalty and performance. On the basis of these assumptions, organization support theory provides a general approach to the role of the reciprocity norm in employee – employer relationships. Hence, it can be summed up that perceived organizational support plays a role in influencing employees work behavior. Employees tend to associate their supervisor's feedback with the organization itself, as such, the feedback they receive should be appropriate. Giving rewards or assistance is not only a criterion for support from one's supervisor, but also from the institution itself. Overall, this study corroborates the argument that organizations that take measures to support their employees and succeed in communicating that support are more likely to retain employees who are committed to their work and to the organization.

Recommendations

Providing a good work environment means ensuring that resources are allocated fairly among staff, and that organizational procedures are applied impartially. Performance should be fairly rated. By this, management of these institutions can be considering each faculty's responsibilities. Supervisory support implies giving employees a chance to participate in decision making, taking their opinions and goals into account, and helping them overcome problems at work. Management of federal tertiary institutions should also review their management procedures in order to create a positive work environment which will help them retain their faculties. Administrators may have to transform their structure from nonchalant attitude towards business educators' complaints to a swift response one; this may account for their employees' goals, values and wellbeing, and see their input as a valuable contribution on how the organization functions as a whole.

References

- Allen, N. and Meyer, P. (1996). Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to the Organization: An examination of construct validity. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 49(1), 252-276
- Baridam, D. (2002). *Management and Organization Theory*. 3rd edition. Port Harcourt Sherbrooke Associates.
- Blau, P. (1964). *Exchange and Power in social Life*, New York: Wiley
- Bodla, A., Afza, T. and Danish, O. (2014). Relationship between organizational politics perceptions and employees' performance, mediating role of social exchange perceptions, *Pakistan Journal of commerce and social science*. 8(2), 426-444.

Original Article

- Budi, P. and Mugi, H. (2023). The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Performance during Organizational Change with Affective Commitment to Change as Mediator. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Research*, 7(6) 179-194
- Chen, Z. (2010). Test of a mediation model of perceived organizational support. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 66(3), 457–470
- Coetzee, M. and Botha, J. (2012). The Languishment of Employee Commitment in the Light of Perceptions of Fair Treatment in the Workplace. *SA Journal of Human Resource*, 1(1), 111
- Darolia, C., Kumari, P. and Darolia, S. (2010). Perceived Organizational Support, work motivation and organization commitment as determinants of Job Performance. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*. 36(1), 69-78.
- Devaraju, M. and Ashoka, M. (2015). A study of factors influencing Retention Strategy of small, medium and large IT sectors in Bangalore City. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*. 6(8), 5749-5752.
- Dixit, V. and Bhati, M. (2012). A Study about Employee Commitment and its impact on sustained productivity in Indian Auto-Component Industry. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 1(6), 34-51
- Dian, E. and Mirza, A. (2008). Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and Organizational Commitment. *Journal of Theory and Applied Management* 1(2):96-108
- Efi, A. and Imagha, O. (2016) Perceived Organizational Support and Turnover Intention of Academic Staff in University of Uyo. *International Journal of Management Studies, Business & Entrepreneurship Research*, 1 (2), 68-82
- Eisenberger, S. Huntington, R., Hutchinson, S. and Sowa, D. (1986). Perceived Organizational Support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71, 500-507
- Fabiene, E. and Kachchhap, S. (2016). Determinants of Employees' Commitment among Healthcare professionals. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accountin, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(2), 44-52
- Gautam, T., VanDick, R. and Wagner, U. (2001). Organizational Commitment in Nepalese settings. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 4(1), 239-248
- Gouldner, A. (1960). The norm of reciprocity: A preliminary statement. *American Sociological Review*, 25(2), 161–178.
- Hang-Yue, N., Loi, R., Foley, Sharon, Z., Xiaoming, S. and Zhang, L. (2010). Perceptions of Organizations context and Job Attitudes/ the mediating effect of Organizational Identification. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 1(1). 65-104.

Original Article

- Imagha, O., Akpaetor, U., Akpan, V. and Atakpo, E. (2023). Exploring the influence of Work Environment on Employees' Commitment in Selected Oil Servicing Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management* 9 (10), 145-171
- Igbal, S. and Hashmi, M. (2015). Impact of perceived Organizational Support on Employee Retention with Mediating Role of Psychological Empowerment. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*. 9(1), 18-34
- Kurtessis, J. N., Eisenberger, R., Ford, M. T., Buffardi, L. C., Stewart, K. A., and Adis, C. S. (2017). Perceived organizational support: A meta-analytic evaluation of organizational support theory. *Journal of Management*, 43(6), 1854-1884.
- Malik, S., Kazmi, S. and Nadeem, N. (2016). The effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Doctors' organizational commitment in Pakistan. *The Lahore journal of Business*, 4(2), 7392
- Meyer, P. and Allen, N. (1991). The measurement and Antecedents of Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to the Organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 3(1), 118
- Rahman, S. and Karan, R. (2012). Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment: Bangladesh Perspective. *The Chittagong University Journal of Business Administration*, 27(1), 205-220
- Rhoades, L. and Eisenberger, R. (2002). Perceived Organizational Support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71(2), 500-507
- Rhodes, L., Eisenberger, R. and Amali, S. (2001). Affective Commitment to the Organization: The Contribution of Perceived Organizational Support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(5), 825-836
- Robbins, S. and Judge, T. (2009). *Organizational Behaviour* (13th edition). USA. Pearson Prentice Hall
- Wayne, S. J., Shore, L. M., and Liden, R. C. (1997). Perceived organizational support and leader member exchange: A social exchange perspective. *Academy of Management Journal*, 40(1), 82–111.